

Analyzing Of Articles On Blue Economy Studies In Tourism

Turizmde Mavi Ekonomi Çalışmaları Üzerine Makalelerin Analizi

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Abstract

The concept of a blue economy, as an approach closely related to tourism, has been studied very limitedly in the field of tourism despite its importance and existential mission. The existing literature has been discussed mainly conceptually. No study has been found that reveals the details of the studies directly related to the blue economy and tourism and evaluates these studies in general. In this context, this study aims to present a bibliometric overview of the studies on the concept of blue economy in tourism in the Web of Science database. In the study, 74 articles on blue economy in tourism published in the Web of Science (WOS) database between 2015 and 2024 constituted the research sample. As a result of the bibliometric analysis of relevant articles, it was determined that studies on the blue economy experienced a slight growth trend followed by a decline. Studies from the United Kingdom, Spain, and the USA were among the most prominent. The most frequently used research method was qualitative research, especially document analysis. Although this study is limited to the WOS database, it is obvious that the visibility and citationability of these studies could be much higher. Despite the critical role of coastal and marine tourism in global maritime trade, it has been noted that blue economy and tourism-oriented studies have not received the recognition they deserve. This is particularly remarkable considering that three-quarters of the Earth's surface is covered by water and the increasing importance of coastal and marine tourism.

Keywords: Blue Economy, Blue Growth, Sustainable Development, Tourism, Vosviewer, Web Of Science.

JEL Codes: A12,F01,L83

Özet

Turizmle yakından ilişkili olan bir yaklaşım olarak mavi ekonomi kavramı, önemine ve varoluş misyonuna rağmen, turizm alanında oldukça sınırlı çalışılan bir konudur ve varolan literatür daha çok kavramsal düzeyde ele alınmıştır. Doğrudan mavi ekonomi ve turizm ile ilişkili yapılan çalışmaların detayını ortaya koyan ve bu çalışmaları genel olarak değerlendiren bir çalışmaya rastlanmamıştır. Bu bağlamda bu çalışmanın amacı, Web of Science veri tabanında bulunan mavi ekonomi kavramını turizmde ele alan çalışmaların bibliyometrik bir genel bakışını sunmaktır. Çalışmada, Web of Science (WOS) veritabanında 2015 ile 2024 yılları arasında yayınlanmış mavi ekonomi üzerine turizmde yapılan 74 makale araştırma örneklemini oluşturmuştur. İlgili makalelerin bibliyometrik analizi sonucunda, mavi ekonomi üzerine yapılan çalışmaların hafif bir büyüme trendi yaşadığı, ardından bir düşüşe geçtiği belirlenmiştir. Birleşik Krallık, İspanya ve ABD kaynaklı çalışmalar en öne çıkanlar arasında yer almıştır. En sık kullanılan araştırma yöntemi nitel araştırma, özellikle doküman analizi olmuştur. Bu çalışma Web of Science (WOS) veritabanı ile sınırlı olsa da bu çalışmaların görünürlüğü ve atıf alabilirliğinin çok daha yüksek olabileceği aşikardır. Kıyı ve deniz turizminin küresel deniz ticaretindeki önemli rolüne rağmen, mavi ekonomi ve turizm odaklı çalışmaların hak ettiği tanınırlığı alamadığı kaydedilmiştir. Bu durum, Dünya yüzeyinin dörtte üçünün suyla kaplı olduğu ve kıyı ve deniz turizminin artan önemi göz önünde bulundurulduğunda özellikle dikkat çekicidir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Mavi Ekonomi, Mavi Büyüme, Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma, Turizm, Vosviewer, Web Of Science.

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Introduction

Türkiye, The concept of the Blue Economy, which focuses on the use and protection of marine resources and supports sustainable development, has emerged as a paradigm in recent years, particularly in the maritime sector (Çalım, 2023). The concept of the Blue Economy was first included in the book "The Blue Economy: 10 Years, 100 Innovations, 100 Million Jobs" published by Gunter Pauli in 2010 and later used at the United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development in Rio de Janeiro in June 2012. Since then it has been actively used (Suluk, 2022). The blue economy, directly related to sustainable development goals, is also closely related to many sectors. Sectors such as fishing, tourism, and maritime transportation are especially closely associated with the blue economy (Yılmaz, 2020).

Sectors such as fisheries, coastal tourism, ports, renewable energy (wind, tides, waves, etc.), and marine logistics are considered part of the blue economy. Sustainable practices in these sectors contribute to economic development (Guerreiro, 2021). The blue economy aims to manage water resources efficiently to preserve them as valuable natural resources for current and future generations (OECD, 2016). According to the EU Blue Economy Report (2023), blue economy sectors created nearly 3,5 million jobs and contributed EUR 129.1 billion in gross value added (GVA) in 2020. (contributing 1.1% to the EU-27 economy), a 30%-decrease from €185.4 billion (1.5% of the EU-27 economy) in 2019. Employment decreased 26% from 4.50 million in 2019 to 3.34 million in 2020 (1.8% in terms of contribution to the EU27 economy). Coastal tourism is among the most impacted. Because Coastal tourism is at the forefront of BE's economic sectors (Kabil et al., 2021)

The concept of the blue economy is an important issue that should be addressed from the perspective of the tourism sector, taking into account the factors that constitute the supply sources of tourism. It has begun to find a place in studies over the last 10 years (see also: Birchenough, 2023; Garza-Gil, Varela-Lafuente & Perez-Perez, 2021; Henderson, 2019; Karani & Failler, 2020; Rogerson & Rogerson, 2019; Vázquez, García & Valenciano, 2021; Vrontisi et al., 2022). Although it is closely related to the tourism sector, the number of studies related to tourism has remained limited (see also: Cummings & Greenberg, 2022; Hall, 2021; Karani et al., 2020; Phelan, Ruhanen & Mair, 2020). Studies related to tourism are most often associated with coastal tourism (Karani et al., 2020; Tegal & Gurning, 2018;). However, the issue is closely related to the tourism sector. Fishing, for example, is one of the most important recreational activities for the tourism industry (Hall, 2021). Recreational fishing includes both ocean and coastal activities and inland fishing on lakes and rivers, which can be extremely important for tourism (Hall & Härkönen, 2006).

As a matter of fact, the blue economy, which concerns many tourism-related issues from coastal tourism to yacht tourism and fishing activities, is an issue that needs to be addressed in terms of creating income sources in tourism, sustainability of the tourism market and protecting the seas and biodiversity in the future. In this context, this study deals with the tourism sector, which is a part of the blue economy. Considering the economic added value and employment opportunities created by the blue economy, it is essential to determine new strategies on the subject. In this context, the study aims to determine the current state of the literature on the blue economy and tourism, thus creating a guide for future studies. Although there has been a similar study in which coastal tourism and the blue economy were discussed together before (Kabil et al., 2021), it is thought to be important and contribute to the literature in that there is no study in which the concepts of blue economy and tourism are discussed together, which deals with the subject from a broader perspective. Depending on the purpose of the study, the blue economy phenomenon in tourism was analyzed by bibliometric analysis. This study aims to reveal the current status of studies on blue economy and tourism, identify gaps in the literature, and offer suggestions for future studies. Therefore, this study will be useful in providing information for those working in this field as a starting point and contributing to the literature.

Conceptual Framework

The concept of a blue economy, which emerged to protect oceans, seas, and water resources, includes all kinds of economic activities carried out in waters, covering sectors such as fishing, tourism, or maritime transportation (Bax et al., 2022). Studies in the literature on blue growth, blue development, and blue economy are mainly discussed together with issues related to climate change, marine ecosystems, and sustainable use of marine resources. (Armstrong et al., 2019; Graziano et al., 2022). In their study, Armstrong et al. (2019) determine the effects of human activities and climate change on deep-sea ecosystems and define the risk levels of these effects on ecosystem services. To this end, it contributes to promoting the sustainable use of deep-sea resources within the framework of blue growth and marine space planning (MSP). In his study, Hassanali (2022) aimed to examine the legal and political documents and organizational regulations that direct the development and implementation of regional ocean management and blue economy policies within CARICOM (Caribbean Community).

According to the study, CARICOM needs to be more sensitive, holistic, and cross-sectional while making policies about ocean management and the blue economy. Existing literature studies focus on the definition of the blue economy and its definitions rela-

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ted to maritime, oceans, and coasts. Studies on its relationship with tourism have mainly been evaluated on the coasts. Kamil et al. (2022), blue economy, and coastal tourism were discussed together, and bibliometric analysis and a quantitative meta-analysis were chosen as a literature review method to determine the research topics and publication patterns of studies in this field. As a result of the research, the number of publications in the blue economy scientific sector has increased significantly.

In contrast, despite the critical role of the coastal tourism sector in the blue economy, there are relatively few studies on coastal tourism in the blue economy literature. In the study conducted by Tegar and Gurning (2018), the effects of sea and coastal tourism and whether it is compatible with other human activities are discussed within the scope of the blue economy. The study reveals that the concepts of blue economy and ecotourism can reduce the environmental impacts of marine and coastal tourism and, at the same time, promote economic growth. Picken (2023) reveals that the concept of blue economy should be considered within the framework of the blue economy of marine tourism, coastal tourism, and freshwater tourism activities. In his study, he argues that tourism academics can contribute to developing the blue economy concept and ensure that tourism-related activities are handled more effectively in planning and policy development processes.

Methodology

The bibliometric method is a technique that is becoming widespread in the field of tourism and examines various features of printed publications through numerical analysis. This method provides important clues about the scientific communication process of the relevant field (Temizkan et al., 2015: 394). Thanks to bibliometric analysis, it becomes possible to classify these studies according to the direction in which the studies in the field of tourism are progressing, the topics discussed and their perspectives. These analyzes can provide researchers with predictions for future studies on how studies in the field of tourism can be improved (Oruç & Türkay, 2017). As men-

tioned in the previous parts of the study, the blue economy and tourism are inseparable fields. Despite this, it does not receive the value it deserves in the literature. To present this view concretely, this study was prepared with the bibliometric analysis method. In this context, this study aims to examine the articles published in journals scanned in the Web of Science database, specifically on the concepts of "blue economy" and "tourism", and make some findings and suggestions. In line with the purpose of the study, a screening was carried out on the following research:

- In which years and how often were the studies carried out?
- What is the distribution of the journals in which the studies are published?
- What is the author-country distribution of the studies?
- What are the main research methods used in the studies?
- What are the main keywords used in the studies?
- What is the distribution of citations to studies?

In this context, a literature review was conducted on the Web of Science database between 15.06.2024 and 15.07.2024. Before starting the research, some filters were used throughout the system. First of all, only articles were included in the research. In addition, due to the language barrier and accessibility concerns, open access and English language options were preferred. In line with the purpose of the research, the keywords "blue economy" and "tourism" were used in quotations to initiate the search process. After searching with the keywords "blue economy" and "tourism," the total of 148 studies that emerged was reduced to 74 articles due to our limitations, and the analysis process was conducted on these 74 articles. While presenting the analysis results, the clustering and visualization feature of the VOSviewer program was utilized.

Findings

The information resulting from the literature review is presented in tabulated form in Table 1 below.

Table 1. The results of the literature review

Reference	Year	Title	Journal	Country	Keywords	Method	Citation Number
Pinto, Cruz & Combe	2015	Cooperation and the emergence of maritime clusters in the Atlantic: Analysis and implications of innovation and human capital for blue growth	Marine Policy	Portugal, Spain, Ireland and Scotland	Absorptive capacity, Innovation, Human capital, LOGIT, Maritime cluster, Proximity, Social capital	Quantitative / surveys	48

Bond	2019	Blue Economy threats, contradictions and resistances seen from South Africa	Journal of Political Ecology	South Africa	Blue Economy, capitalist crisis, Oceans Phakisa, resistance, South Africa	Conceptualized	27
Rogerson & Rogerson	2019	Emergent planning for South Africa's blue economy: Evidence from coastal and marine tourism	Urban Izziv-Urban Challenge	South Africa	blue economy, special planning, Operation Phakisa, coastal and marine tourism, South Africa	Qualitative / document analysis	14
van den Burg et al.	2019	Assessment of the geographical potential for co-use of marine space, based on operational boundaries for Blue Growth sectors	Marine Policy	European Atlantic, Baltic/ North Sea, Mediterranean/Black Sea and the Caribbean/ Gulf of Mexico	Aquaculture, Blue Growth, Blue Economy, Marine spatial planning, Marine governance	Qualitative / Marine Spatial Planning	41
Armstrong et al.	2019	Expert Assessment of Risks Posed by Climate Change and Anthropogenic Activities to Ecosystem Services in the Deep North Atlantic	Frontiers in Marine Science	North Atlantic Ocean	ecosystem services, climate change, anthropogenic impacts, risk, deep sea, North Atlantic Ocean, blue growth	Quantitative / surveys	16
Henderson	2019	Oceans without History? Marine Cultural Heritage and the Sustainable Development Agenda	Sustainability	Global	Marine Cultural Heritage; maritime archaeology; sustainable development; SDG 14; resilience; Blue Economy; Ocean Science	Conceptualized	29
McKinley et al.	2019	Charting the course for a blue economy in Peru: a research agenda	Environment, Development and Sustainability	Peru	Blue growth, Blue economy, Marine, Society, Sustainability	Conceptualized	33
Gustavsson & Morrissey	2019	A typology of different perspectives on the spatial economic impacts of marine spatial planning	Journal Of Environmental Policy & Planning	United Kingdom	Marine spatial planning; Q methodology; Blue Economy; spatial economic impacts; typology	Quantitative	9
Said & MacMillan	2020	'Re-grabbing' marine resources: a blue degrowth agenda for the resurgence of small-scale fisheries in Malta	Sustainability Science	Malta	Neoliberalism, Tuna, Conservation policies, Sustainable development goals, Community economies, Redistribution	Qualitative / Q-method	25

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Hoerterer et al.	2020	Stakeholder Perspectives on Opportunities and Challenges in Achieving Sustainable Growth of the Blue Economy in a Changing Climate	Frontiers In Marine Science	Germany	Adaptation, fisheries, tourism, North Sea, aquaculture, blue growth, seafood	Qualitative / interview	14
Rasowo et al.	2020	Harnessing Kenya's Blue Economy: prospects and challenges	Journal Of The Indian Ocean Region	Kenya	Blue Economy, sustainable development, governance, COVID-19	Qualitative / content analysis	6
Karani & Failler	2020	Comparative coastal and marine tourism, climate change, and the blue economy in African Large Marine Ecosystems	Environmental Development	Africa	Blue economy, Coastal and marine tourism, Climate resilience, Environment, Blue carbon & ecosystem services, Infrastructure, Development, Large marine ecosystems (LMEs), Africa	Conceptualized	36
Roos, Kubina & Farafonova	2021	Opportunities For Sustainable Economic Development of The Coastal Territories of The Baltic Sea Region in The Context of Digital Transformation	Baltic Region	Russian Federation (St. Petersburg, Leningrad, Kaliningrad) and 21 EU territories	Baltic Sea Region, sustainable development, blue economy, digitalisation	Conceptualized	3
Garza-Gil, Varela-Lafuente & Perez-Perez	2021	The Blue Economy in the European Union: Valuation of Spanish Small-Scale Fishers' Perceptions on Environmental and Socioeconomic Effects	Panoeconomic	European Union	Perceptions and attitudes, environmental-economic synergies, blue economy, small-scale fishing, coastal management	Quantitative / survey	3
Lazarus & Ziros	2021	Yachts and marinas as hotspots of coastal risk	Anthropocene Coasts	Mediterranean	Yachts, marinas, coastal risk, safe-development paradox, Mediterranean, insurance	Conceptualized	8
Martínez-Vázquez, García & Valenciano	2021a	Analysis and Trends of Global Research on Nautical, Maritime and Marine Tourism	Journal Of Marine Science and Engineering	Global	bibliometric indicators, marine tourism, maritime tourism, nautical tourism, web of science, Scopus	Qualitative/ bibliometric analysis	29

Huang & Mabon	2021	Coastal landscapes, sustainable consumption and peripheral communities: Evaluating the Miramar Resort controversy in Shanyuan Bay, Taiwan	Marine Policy	Taiwan	Coastal landscapes, Qualitative research, Sustainable consumption, Sustainable tourism, Taiwan	Qualitative / interview	3
Luhtala et al.	2021	Business sector involvement in maritime spatial planning - Experiences from the Baltic Sea region	Marine Policy	Baltic Sea (European Union countries apart from Russia)	Marine spatial planning, Stakeholder involvement, Planning process, Business representatives, Baltic Sea	Qualitative / interview	6
Kabil et al.	2021	Blue Economy and Coastal Tourism: A Comprehensive Visualization Bibliometric Analysis	Sustainability	Global	blue economy (BE); coastal tourism; bibliometric analysis; R language; CiteSpace; VOSviewer; visualization	Qualitative/ bibliometric analysis	34
Vega-Muñoz et al.	2021	Port Governance and Cruise Tourism	Sustainability	Global	blue economy, seaport, cruise terminal, stakeholder, tourism, cooperation, competition, cruise ship	Qualitative/ Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses	1
Mach & Ponting	2021	Establishing a pre-COVID-19 baseline for surf tourism: Trip expenditure and attitudes, behaviors and willingness to pay for sustainability	Annals of Tourism Research Empirical Insights	Global	Surf tourism, Sustainability, Blue economy, Tourist preferences, Willingness to pay, COVID-19	Quantitative / survey	19
Minelli et al.	2021	The ADRIREEF database: a comprehensive collection of natural/ artificial reefs and wrecks in the Adriatic Sea	Earth System Science Data	Adriatic Region	Dive Tourism, Coral-Reefs, Marine	Quantitative / survey	3
Martínez-Vázquez, García & Valenciano	2021b	Challenges of the Blue Economy: evidence and research trends	Environmental Sciences Europe	Global	Blue Economy, Blue growth, Ocean economy, Maritime economy, Marine economy, Bibliometric analysis	Qualitative/ bibliometric analysis	37
Praptiwi et al.	2021	Tourism-Based Alternative Livelihoods for Small Island Communities Transitioning towards a Blue Economy	Sustainability	Indonesia	Sustainable livelihoods, eco-tourism; alternative livelihoods; conservation development; marine planning; blue economy	Qualitative/ focus group, interview, secondary data	18

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Schutter et al.	2021a	The blue economy as a boundary object for hegemony across scales	Marine Policy	Seychelles	Blue growth, Ocean economy, Ocean governance, Sustainable development, Small Island developing states	Mixed-method	26
Schutter et al.	2021b	Disentangling ecosystem services preferences and values	World Development	Seychelles	Fisheries, Tourism, Management, Decision-making, Trade-offs, Marine, Coral reef, Conservation	Mixed-method	4
Hall	2021	Tourism and fishing	Scandinavian Journal of Hospitality and Tourism	Global	Blue Economy; Blue Growth; marine ecosystem services; marine tourism; Sustainable Development Goals	Conceptualized	10
Agius & Briguglio	2021	Mitigating seasonality patterns in an archipelago: the role of ecotourism	Maritime Studies	Italy	Seasonality, Ecotourism, Archipelago, Central Mediterranean, Blue economy, Aegadian Islands	Qualitative / interview	8
Fassbender et al.	2021	Reef benthos of Seychelles - A field guide	Biodiversity Data Journal	Seychelles	coral reefs, mesophotic coral ecosystems, benthos, morphotype, Seychelles, Indian Ocean	Qualitative/ Field Trip	4
Bacciu et al.	2021	Investigating the Climate-Related Risk of Forest Fires for Mediterranean Islands' Blue Economy	Sustainability	Mediterranean	Mediterranean islands; forest fires; fire weather; impact chains; blue economy; EUROCORDERX; future climate projections; H2020 SOCLIMPACT	Mixed-method	10
Guerreiro	2021	The Blue Growth Challenge to Maritime Governance	Frontiers In Marine Science	European Union and Atlantic countries	blue growth, maritime governance, ocean economy, marine policy, maritime spatial planning	Qualitative/ document analysis	6
Hietala et al.	2021	Data integration and participatory process in developing integrated coastal zone management (ICZM) in the northern Baltic Sea	Journal Of Coastal Conservation	Estonia and Finland	Coastal planning · Land-sea interaction · MSP · Public participation	Qualitative/ document analysis	7

Vega-Muñoz, Salazar-Sepúlveda & Contreras-Barraza	2021	Identifying the Blue Economy Global Epistemic Community	Water	Global	environmental; coastal; Blue Economy; politics; aquaculture; energy	Qualitative/ bibliometric analysis	5
Song & Fabinyi	2022	China's 21st century maritime silk road: Challenges and opportunities to coastal livelihoods in ASEAN countries	Marine Policy	China	China, ASEAN, 21st Century maritime silk road, Chinese maritime investment, Coastal livelihoods	Qualitative/ document analysis	18
Leuci et al.	2022	Trends in sandy beach variability EThekwini Municipality, South Africa	Journal Of Sea Research	South Africa	coastal erosion, shoreline migration, coastal management, sandy shoreline, sandy beach, river impoundment	Quantitative/ morphological data analysis	1
Gazal, Andrew & Burns	2022	Economic Contributions of Visitor Spending in Ocean Recreation in the Florida Keys National Marine Sanctuary	Water	United States	economic contribution analysis; input-output modelling; marine sanctuaries; visitor spending	Quantitative/ survey	4
Niner et al.	2022	Issues of context, capacity and scale: Essential conditions and missing links for a sustainable blue economy	Environmental Science & Policy	Global	sustainable development goals, blue economy, marine governance, marine natural capital, ocean economy, benefit sharing	Qualitative/ systematic literature review	13
Vrontisi et al.	2022	Macroeconomic impacts of climate change on the Blue Economy sectors of southern European islands	Climatic Change	Mediterranean and Atlantic	climate change, climate costs, economic impacts, CGE, blue economy, islands	Quantitative	11
Sakellariadou et al.	2022	Seabed mining and blue growth: exploring the potential of marine mineral deposits as a sustainable source of rare earth elements (Ma-REEs) (IUPAC Technical Report)	Pure And Applied Chemistry	Asia-Pacific and mid-Atlantic	Deep-sea ecosystems; environmental impacts; ferromanganese crusts; IUPAC chemistry and the environment division; polymetallic nodules; polymetallic sulfides; rare earth elements; seabed mining	Qualitative/ document analysis	13

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Ruban & Yashalova	2022	Corporate Pro-Environmental Behavior on the Seas: Eco-Ethical Prescriptions of the Largest Cruise Companies	Journal Of Marine Science and Engineering	Global	cruise lines; eco-ethics; marine policy; responsibility; thematic categorization	Qualitative/ document analysis	3
Komninos, Kostopoulos & Garofalakis	2022	Automatic generation of sailing holiday itineraries using vessel density data and semantic technologies	Information Technology & Tourism	Greece	Maritime trip planning, Vessel routing, Route planning, Itinerary, Recommendation, Genetic algorithms, Semantic spatial modeling	Qualitative/ document analysis	0
Graziano et al.	2022	The many sizes and characters of the Blue Economy	Ecological Economics	Scotland and Michigan	Blue Economy, Regional analysis, Employment, Wages	Qualitative/ document analysis	8
Tanaka et al.	2022	Spatial distribution maps of real-time ocean observation platforms and sensors in Japanese waters	Marine Policy	Japan	Ocean observatory, Maritime domain awareness, capacity building, blue economy	Qualitative/ case study, observation	1
Hassanali	2022	Examining Institutional Arrangements toward Coordinated Regional Ocean Governance and Blue Economy Policy Development in the Caribbean Community (CARICOM)	Coastal Management	Caribbean	blue growth; Caribbean Community; regional integration; regional ocean governance; sustainable ocean-economy	Qualitative/ document analysis	2
Martínez-Vázquez, Valenciano & García	2022	Impact Analysis of Marinas on Nautical Tourism in Andalusia	Journal Of Marine Science and Engineering	Spain	blue economy; local development; nautical sector; tourism	Qualitative / interview	3
Glass et al.	2022	Evaluating the Feasibility of Sustainable Seafood Labelling Programmes in Small Island Developing States: A Pilot Study of Artisanal Fisheries in Seychelles	Frontiers In Marine Science	Seychelles	market-based instruments, eco-label, emerging economy, marine fisheries, blue economy, small island developing states (SIDS), Indian Ocean, Africa	Qualitative / interview	2

Kabil et al.	2022	Tourism centres efficiency as spatial unites for applying blue economy approach: A case study of the Southern Red Sea region, Egypt	Plos One	Egypt	Data Envelopment Analysis, Industry	Quantitative/ Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) and Free Disposal Hull (FDH)	6
Pita et al.	2022	Economic contribution and social welfare of recreational charter boat fisheries in the northeast Atlantic: The cases of Galicia (Spain) and Madeira archipelago (Portugal)	Frontiers In Marine Science	Portugal	travel cost method, marine recreational fisheries, economic contribution, big game fishing, blue economy	Mixed method	3
Pournara & Sakellariadou	2022	Development of a Protocol for a Sustainable Blue Economy in the Coastal Zone: Case Study and Preliminary Results in a Coastal Industrial Area in the Eastern Mediterranean	Sustainability	Greece	sustainable blue economy; integrated coastal zone management; shipyard; industry; tourism	Qualitative/ case study	5
Liang et al.	2022	Bibliometrics and visualization analysis of research in the field of sustainable development of the blue economy (2006-2021)	Frontiers In Marine Science	Global	blue economy, sustainable development, bibliometrics, CiteSpace, VOSviewer, research trends	Qualitative/ bibliometric analysis	5
Salgado-Gómez et al.	2022	Perceptions Environmental and Health Impacts of Cruise Activity in the Roatan Ports	Water	Honduras	blue economy; tourism; cruiser; stakeholders	Qualitative / interview	0
Santos, Castanho & Meyer	2022	Is Investment Contributing to Competitiveness in Nautical Tourism in the Atlantic Area?	Water	Ireland, Portugal, Spain, United Kingdom, France	Atlantic Area; blue economy; competitiveness; corporate performance; investment; nautical tourism	Qualitative/ document analysis	4
Booth, Mourato & Milner-Gulland	2022	Investigating acceptance of marine tourism levies, to cover the opportunity costs of conservation for coastal communities	Ecological Economics	Indonesia	Contingent valuation, payments for ecosystem services, willingness to pay, Indonesia, sharks, elasmobranchs, endangered species, conservation finance, blue economy, sustainable development	Mixed method	4

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Troian et al.	2023	International Marine Tourism: Trends and Prospects for Sustainable Development	Pomorsto-Scientific Journal of Maritime Research	Global	International marine tourism, Sustainable development, Tourism prospects, Sustainable tourism, Bibliographic review	Qualitative/ bibliographic and content analysis	2
Martínez-Vázquez et al.	2023	Impact of blue economy sectors using causality, correlation and panel data models	Frontiers In Marine Science	European Union	blue economy factors, correlation, causality, panel data model, sustainability	Quantitative	2
Pranita et al.	2023	Blockchain Technology to Enhance Integrated Blue Economy: A Case Study in Strengthening Sustainable Tourism on Smart Islands	Sustainability	Indonesia	smart destination; blockchain technology; blue economy; digital literacy; sustainable tourism	Mixed method	9
Spalding et al.	2023	Nature dependent tourism-combining big data and local knowledge	Journal Of Environmental Management	Dominica, Grenada, Saint Kitts and Nevis, Saint Lucia, and Saint Vincent and the Grenadines	Blue economy, User-generated content, Ecosystem services, Eastern Caribbean, Nature dependent tourism, Wildlife tourism	Quantitative	2
Mejjad et al.	2023	Marine plastic pollution in Morocco: state of the knowledge on origin, occurrence, fate, and management	Environmental Science and Pollution Research	Morocco	Plastic waste, Marine pollution, Waste management, Circular economy, Morocco	Qualitative/ document analysis	5
Rogerson & Rogerson	2023	Historical geographies of coastal tourism: Mossel Bay, South Africa c.1850-1988	Bulletin Of Geography-Socio-Economic Series	South Africa	blue economy, coastal tourism, historical geography, Mossel Bay, South Africa	Qualitative/ document analysis	1
Van Putten et al.	2023	History matters: societal acceptance of deep-sea mining and incipient conflicts in Papua New Guinea	Maritime Studies	Papua New Guinea	Deep sea, Mining, Papua New Guinea, Social licence, Marine conflict	Qualitative/ document analysis	2
Manero & Mach	2023	Valuing surfing ecosystems: an environmental economics and natural resources management perspective	Tourism Geographies	Global	surfing economics; ecosystem services; blue economy; ocean values; surfing resources; non-market valuation; surf tourism	Conceptualized	1

Birchenough	2023	Knowledge-based science in support of the blue growth ambition for small island developing states	Ices Journal of Marine Science	Global	climate change, data, finance, fisheries, habitat mapping, SIDS, technology.	Conceptualized	0
Pagano et al.	2023	Multicriteria GIS-based analysis for the evaluation of the vulnerability of the marine environment in the Gulf of Trieste (north-eastern Adriatic Sea) for sustainable blue economy and maritime spatial planning	People and Nature	Italy	Adriatic Sea, Gulf of Trieste, multicriteria Geographic Information System-based analysis, protected areas, vulnerability of the marine environment, vulnerability of the sea bed	Qualitative/document analysis	2
Jattak et al.	2023	Advancing the initiatives of sustainable coastal and marine areas development in Pakistan through marine spatial planning	Science Progress	Pakistan	Pakistan marine spatial planning, ecosystem health, blue economy development, social inclusion, PESTLE analysis	Qualitative/document analysis	1
Makarova et al.	2023	The Construction of Seaports in the Arctic: Prospects and Environmental Consequences	Journal of Marine Science and Engineering	Russia	"Blue economy"; seaports; Northern Sea Route (NSR); environmental safety; anthropogenic factor; anthropogenic pollution; ontological engineering; risk management system	Qualitative/document analysis	2
Fernández-Palacios et al.	2023	Status and perspectives of blue economy sectors across the Macaronesian archipelagos	Journal Of Coastal Conservation	Portugal, Spain	Maritime Sectors and Activities, Trends, Blue Growth, Maritime Spatial Planning, Ecosystem Approach, Azores, Madeira, Canary Islands	Qualitative/document analysis	1
Kyriazi et al.	2023	Conceptualising Marine Biodiversity Mainstreaming as an Enabler of Regional Sustainable Blue Growth: The Case of the European Atlantic Area	Sustainability	European Union	sustainable blue growth; blue economy sectors; marine biodiversity mainstreaming; blue economy sectors; natural capital valuation; sea basin; European Atlantic	Qualitative/document analysis	0

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Ferretti et al.	2023	Restorative practices, marine ecotourism, and restoration economies: revitalizing the environmental agenda?	Ecology and Society	Global	citizen science; dive tourism; marine ecological restoration; restorative economies; restorative marine ecotourism; socialecological systems	Conceptualized	0
Fidai et al.	2024	Innovative spectral characterisation of beached pelagic sargassum towards remote estimation of biochemical and phenotypic properties	Science Of the Total Environment	Barbados and Ghana	Macroalgae, Remote sensing, Marine ecosystems, Coastal management, Sargassum	Quantitative/ survey	1
Tsai et al.	2024	Urban Governance, Economic Transformation, and Land Use: A Case Study on the Jimei Peninsula, Xiamen, China, 1936-2023	Water	China	heterogeneous; embeddedness; moments; commodity; consumption landscape	Qualitative / interview	0
de Carvalho-Souza et al.	2024	How to deal with invasive species that have high economic value?	Biological Conservation	Spain	Non-indigenous species, New resource exploitation, Integrated participatory strategy, Citizen science, Blue economy	Qualitative/ case study	0
de la Vara et al.	2024	Climate change impacts on the tourism sector of the Spanish Mediterranean coast: Medium-term projections for a climate services tool	Climate Services	Spain	Climate change, Climate modelling, Future projections, Coastal tourism, Climate adaptation, Spanish Mediterranean coast, Climate service tool	Qualitative/ climate modelling	0
Kim, Scott & Swartz	2024	Local perspectives on marine ecotourism development in a water-insecure island region: the case of Bocas del Toro, Panama	Frontiers In Marine Science	Panama	marine ecotourism, water security, blue economy, island systems, Bocas del Toro, sustainable development	Qualitative/ interview, observation, document analysis	0
Luoma et al.	2024	Sustainability as a shared objective? Stakeholders' interpretations on the sustainable development of marinas in the Gulf of Finland	Ocean & Coastal Management	Finland	Leisure boating, Coastal tourism, Influence diagrams, Baltic Sea, Blue economy	Qualitative/ interview	0"

In Table 1 above, the following information related to the reviewed articles is summarized: year, author, journal name, country of origin of the article, keywords, method used, and the number of citations. The reason for this is to understand aspects such as the level of interest in the topic, who has shown interest and when, and how the subject has been addressed.

Figure 1: The VOSviewer scheme for the authors of the publications

When looking at authors conducting studies focused on the blue economy and tourism, it is observed that at least three authors predominantly prepare the studies. As shown in Figure 1 above, according to the visual created by the VOSviewer program, there is no specific clustering among the authors working on these topics. On the other hand, in individual searches, the most frequently encountered authors are Martínez-Vázquez, García, and Valencia. The comment that can be made regarding this is that there are no researchers producing works frequently enough to be considered authorities on tourism and blue economy topics.

Figure 2: Yearly publication numbers
Source: Web of Science (2024)

When examining the studies on a yearly basis, the distribution of the studies' publication years is shown in Figure 2 above. In this context, it is observed that

the studies were published between 2015 and 2024, with only a single study on the topic conducted in 2015. The interest in the subject peaked in 2021 and 2022, but subsequently, there has been a declining trend.

Figure 3: The journals where articles were published

Another aspect examined was the journals in which these studies were published. In this context, the main journals where the publications, detailed in Table 1 above, are clustered by VOSviewer are shown in Figure 3. It is observed that most studies related to the topic have been published in the journals Marine Policy, Frontiers in Marine Science and Sustainability.

Figure 4: Research areas of the publications

According to Figure 4 above, the research areas of the publications are seen. More than 82 % of the articles are based on environmental sciences and studies (Web of Science, 2024). Interestingly, the economic-focused articles only account for 5% of the discussion on the blue economy. Therefore, it can be said that studies on the blue economy and tourism appear to focus more on environmental aspects than on economic ones.

Figure 5: The keywords of the articles with a scheme of VOSviewer

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On the other hand, even though the articles' research areas are mainly environmental, the most frequently used keywords are blue economy, blue growth, tourism, sustainable development, ocean economy, and sustainable development goals according to the scheme of VOSviewer in Figure 5.

Figure 6: Countries of the articles scheme of VOSviewer

Data on the countries where the studies were conducted have been examined and illustrated in Figure 6 above. It is known that all the countries where the studies were conducted have coastlines along seas or oceans and derive economic income from marine environments. However, in terms of clustering, most studies have been conducted in England, Spain, and the USA, with these three countries accounting for more than half of the studies conducted.

Figure 7: The most cited articles scheme of VOSviewer

In Figure 7 above, the citations made to published works are shown clustered by author. More detailed numbers are also provided in Table 1 above. According to these data, 10 of the listed works have not yet received any citations. Among the works that have received the most citations are those by Pinto et al., van den Burg et al., and Martinez-Vazquez et al. Overall, the topic has a relatively low citation rate. Finally, the methods used in the studies were examined. In this regard, 46 of the studies were conducted using qualitative research methods and document analysis. Additionally, 12 studies were prepared using quantitative methods, primarily through survey techniques. Ten studies were entirely concep-

tual, and six employed a mixed-methods approach. This indicates that the topic has predominantly been studied using qualitative methods, relying on relevant documents and literature.

Conclusion

The concept of a blue economy has recently become one of the prominent topics as it is closely related to the tourism sector (Kabil et al., 2021). This study aims to contribute to the relevant literature by examining the research on blue economy and tourism within the framework of the determined criteria (year of the study, distribution of the journals in which it was published, author-country distribution, basic research methods, keywords used, and citation).

The results of this research provide important findings in terms of revealing the place of the blue economy concept in tourism and the diversity of studies conducted in this field. 74 articles published in the Web of Science database between 2015 and 2024 were examined and analyzed. In this context, the most striking finding about the study is that despite the importance of coastal and marine tourism in general maritime trade and international tourism mobility, it deserves a different and better position. Blue economy studies in tourism, which have only a 10-year writing history, have already entered a downward trend. Unlike what Martinez-Vazquez et al. (2021b) found in their research, now it is a certain finding that blue economy studies related to tourism are visibly decreasing. However, the issue is also critical in terms of sustainable tourism. Although blue economy scientific production has increased significantly over the years (Kabil et al., 2021), the subject of blue economy and tourism has received relatively less attention in the literature despite the critical role of coastal tourism in the blue economy. The findings reflect changes in research priorities and emerging themes within the academic community, underlining the dynamic nature of academic interest in the blue economy in tourism.

According to the results, England, Spain, and the USA are among the countries that stand out in studies on blue economy and tourism. These countries are considered leaders in this field of research, having produced literature addressing various aspects of the blue economy. Kabil et al. (2021) state that when scientific production related to the blue economy is examined, China, England, Kenya, and the USA emerge as the most productive countries. This shows that research efforts are spread across different continents, underscoring global interest in the blue economy. These findings show that although the blue economy is a globally valid concept, the academic focus on this topic varies across regions.

Many of these studies use qualitative research methods, especially document analysis. This methodo-

logical approach has facilitated an in-depth investigation of the dimensions of the blue economy. In particular, the article titled "Collaboration and the Emergence of Maritime Clusters in the Atlantic: Analysis and Implications of Innovation and Human Capital for Blue Growth" garnered the most citations. This study highlights the critical role of maritime clusters in the Atlantic region, examining their contribution to innovation and human capital development and emphasizing the importance of blue growth. Document analysis is essential because it provides a basis for new studies by reviewing the existing literature and previous research (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2016). On the other hand, the lack of current publications and information may not reflect the current situation. In this respect, quantitative methods can also be used to obtain more generalizable data. Various methodological approaches and geographical representations in the literature enrich our understanding of the multifaceted nature of the blue economy and its implications for sustainable development in the tourism sector.

According to the results of keyword analysis, the terms after "blue economy," "blue growth," and "tourism", "sustainable development, ocean economy, and sustainable development goals" are the most frequent keywords in the literature. This reveals that the blue economy is an important concept in terms of economic development but also in terms of sustainability and environmental protection. The study by Hassanali (2022) also emphasizes the importance of the blue economy in sustainable development, especially in marine areas. The frequent occurrence of these terms in the literature emphasizes the subject's importance and currentness. The fact that the keywords blue economy, blue growth, and tourism come together emphasizes that the issue should be evaluated in terms of its sustainable, economic, and social dimensions. As an essential component of the blue economy, tourism can stimulate economic growth in marine and coastal regions. Tourism, especially based on marine ecosystems, can contribute to local economies. However, the adverse environmental effects of tourism also need to be considered. When discussing coastal tourism, if the blue economy and blue growth issues are discussed together and strategies are developed for this, it will positively affect the sector in practice.

However, the visibility and citation rates of studies focusing on the blue economy and tourism are not as high as they could be. This implies that the number of publications and citations is relatively low compared to the significance of the topic. Just by looking at the number of citations, one can once again witness how low the number of publications on the subject is. Not working on the subject may indicate two issues: first, everyone already knows the subject well and does not need to study. Secondly, the importance of the subject has not been adequately

understood, and the subject has not become a focal point to be studied; in other words, there has not been enough curiosity for research. However, as stated in the conceptual framework, the blue economy is a multidimensional field that concerns the whole world and deserves to be given more importance. Thus, increasing awareness and scholarly engagement with this subject could enhance its academic prominence and highlight its importance in promoting sustainable practices within maritime sectors. This underscores the need for more focused research and greater dissemination of findings to elevate the blue economy's profile within the academic community.

These results reveal that blue economy studies need the attention they deserve, considering that two-thirds of the earth's surface is covered with water and the increasing importance of coastal and marine tourism in the global economy. It is emphasized that future research should examine the different dimensions of the blue economy in more depth and better understand this field's economic, environmental, and social aspects. In this context, promoting sustainable practices and raising awareness about the blue economy should be an essential agenda item both in the academic world and among policymakers. It should not be forgotten that the blue economy is of critical importance in terms of economic development, sustainability, and environmental protection. Therefore, researchers and policymakers must adopt versatile and innovative approaches to unlock the full potential of the blue economy. This situation also shows that the number and citation rates of studies on the blue economy and tourism should be increased. More coverage in academic literature and increased awareness of this issue will contribute to a better understanding of the importance of the blue economy in global maritime trade. This could offer new opportunities for both researchers and policymakers and further strengthen the blue economy's contribution to sustainable development.

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